

MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING SOCIAL PREVENTIVE ACTIVITIES OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IN COOPERATION WITH THE "MAHALLA SEVEN" IN EARLY CRIME PREVENTION

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Abstract. This article presents the main concepts of social preventive activities of internal affairs bodies in cooperation with the "mahalla seven" for early crime prevention, the main directions of activity, issues of cooperation, and key areas for improving collaboration in this field.

Keywords: crime, early prevention, internal affairs bodies, "mahalla seven," activity, cooperation, measures, improvement.

The causes of crimes and the conditions that enable them also change in harmony with the processes, changes, and renewals taking place in society. Today, the main criminogenic determinants that cause and fuel crime in our republic include: unemployment, immorality, dependency, and chronic alcoholism.

Unemployment - the inability of a portion of the economically active population to find suitable work and their transformation into a labor reserve[1]. Unemployment is one of the major socio-economic problems that directly affects human interests. For people, unemployment leads to a decrease in family living standards, instability in personal life, and has a serious psychological impact on individuals.

One of the negative consequences of unemployment is its connection to crime, its "feeding" and growth. One of the most adverse effects of unemployment and lack of socially beneficial work is its link to crime, including organized crime, that is, its "nourishment" and proliferation. Many of the problems and calamities that befall us, especially if we consider the fate of our maturing youth and children, often begin with unemployment.

Analyses show that one in four people who commit crimes in our republic is unemployed[2].

According to criminologists, a 10% increase in unemployment leads to a 3.4-6.5% increase in crime[3].

When studying the causes and conditions of crimes that may be committed as a result of unemployment, it is important, first of all, to analyze the nature of unemployment and the reasons for its occurrence. Unemployment creates material shortages and difficulties in families. As a result, individuals may resort to crime.

The causes of unemployment can be divided into two categories: objective and subjective.

Objective causes of unemployment include: increasing labor productivity and decreasing labor force demand due to technological advancements; disruption of supply and demand balance in the economy, reduction in labor force demand due to decreased market demand for goods; increased demand for skilled labor with the development of the economy and information-communication technologies, eliminating the need for unskilled workers; rapid population growth relative to production, resulting in some becoming surplus and unemployed.

Subjective causes of unemployment include: unemployed individuals' lack of interest in socially beneficial professions and lack of enthusiasm for work; the neglect, carelessness, and indifference of close relatives towards unemployed youth, and their lack of involvement in socially beneficial activities or professions; excessive affection and undemanding attitude of parents towards their children in some families, resulting in the development of a dependency mindset among young people; and the strong desire of some individuals to earn money and enrich themselves through easy and illegal means.

When organizing preventive work with persons who may commit crimes as a result of unemployment, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: creating a list of unemployed persons for the purpose of door-to-door study of unemployed individuals living in families within the mahalla; conducting individual conversations with unemployed persons and providing recommendations on possible work activities; holding discussions with family members or close relatives of unemployed persons during door-to-door visits; studying the interests, abilities, talents, and needs of persons who may commit crimes due to unemployment, as well as problems related to themselves and their lives with the help of professional psychologists; organizing systematic work to provide social, legal, medical, psychological, and other practical assistance during individual educational and preventive conversations with persons who may commit crimes due to unemployment, assigning them mentors from among reputable, experienced citizens of the mahalla; investigating the reasons for the ineffectiveness of efforts to organize meaningful leisure activities for these individuals; conducting educational and preventive work in relation to persons who may commit crimes as a result of unemployment to address identified issues, informing responsible persons who are not fulfilling their duties to provide practical assistance, and if necessary, appealing to the prosecutor in the prescribed manner; keeping constant surveillance of persons who may commit crimes due to unemployment, regularly monitoring their leisure activities and the company they keep; taking measures to provide employment for unemployed citizens through home-based work; cooperating with district employment assistance agencies to find jobs for individuals who may commit crimes due to unemployment, who are not fulfilling their family obligations, and who are wasting their free time unproductively.

In the process of interviews, it is advisable to give the following recommendations to unemployed persons and other family members: to explain the need for other family members to allocate time and engage in the upbringing of unemployed persons; to explain the need to monitor what kind of activity unemployed persons are engaged in throughout the day; to explain the need to identify unemployed persons' desire to earn money or get rich through easy and illegal means and to give recommendations on how to eliminate them; to explain the need to conduct conversations of moral and ethical content in order to prevent unemployed persons from becoming dependent; to explain the need for other family members to set tasks for unemployed persons to engage in certain legal activities and help them in their implementation; to explain the importance of providing explanations to prevent unemployed persons from falling under the influence of spiritually destructive, low-minded and dissatisfied persons; to explain the need for other family members to encourage unemployed persons to engage in socially useful work (stimulate interest) and assist them in employment, as well as to conduct a number of other moral, ethical, and educ

When conducting educational work with unemployed individuals in the family, the use of alternative methods, such as providing them with the necessary care and support, can have a positive effect[4].

The reasons for the emergence of dependency include: some individuals included in the "Iron Notebook," "Women's Notebook," "Youth Notebook," and "Kindness Notebook" in the relevant sector have learned to live without working; some individuals lack interest and desire to work, work, learn a profession, and live on honestly earned money; parents and other adults in the family do not raise children and youth in the spirit of working, learning a profession, and living on honestly earned money, moreover, adults themselves cannot set an example for the younger generation in this regard; unemployed individuals cannot find suitable work or do not have the necessary knowledge (diploma) to work in the work they desire; responsible employees in the sectors do not create enough jobs for the population in the regions, etc.

When organizing preventive work with persons with dependency attitudes, it is necessary to pay attention to the following: collection of information about families and persons with dependency attitudes in the territory of the mahalla with the help of street leaders, heads of households and other persons; conducting door-to-door visits to these families, studying the spiritual and psychological atmosphere and situation in them, as well as studying the factors contributing to their dependency attitudes; organizing preventive and explanatory work to rid families and persons with dependency attitudes from this vice with the involvement of representatives of the general public, involving them in spiritual and educational events organized in the mahalla; ensuring the participation of persons with dependency attitudes, together with mahalla activists, in events to provide assistance to truly low-income and poor families, etc.

Alcoholism is a chronic disease caused by frequent and excessive consumption of alcoholic beverages, accompanied by a strong craving for it. This condition leads to the need for "headaches," specific changes in personality, and somatic (internal) and social consequences. The factor leading to this harmful vice is alcohol.

For the emergence of chronic alcoholism, alcohol alone is not enough; social, psychological, and biological factors participate in its development: social factors include: education, marital status, material well-being, social standing, attitude towards alcoholism, and others; psychological factors include: the good mood, cheerfulness, relief, and desire to "avoid life's difficulties" that alcohol gives to a person; biological factors include: hereditary predisposition, metabolic disorders, particularly vitamin B and C balance, disruption of chlorine and sodium ratios in blood, and imbalance between adrenaline and adrenochrome.

Intoxication (acute alcohol poisoning) is a complex of mental, vegetative, and neurological disorders caused by the psychotropic effects of alcoholic beverages.

One of the social dangers of chronic alcoholism is that it causes somatic diseases, resulting in the death of many people. According to the World Health Organization, alcohol-related diseases rank second after cardiovascular diseases and tumors in terms of mortality rates. According to statistical data from US scientists, the average mortality rate of chronic drinkers is twice as high as that of non-alcoholics. This reduces human life expectancy by 17-18 years[5].

Alcoholism has a significant impact on the nation's gene pool. Because newborns are born mentally and physically weak. As a result of this harmful disease, a person loses their health and their work activity decreases. Also, mutual disagreements and family breakdown occur in

the family. The human qualities of a person disappear, and this person transitions to a lifestyle without working. Treatment and rehabilitation of those who have embarked on this path requires enormous funds. In general, regular consumption of alcoholic beverages has a great negative impact on the family and society.

Another socially dangerous aspect of chronic alcoholism is the commission of crimes by individuals suffering from it. Studies show that the higher the level of alcoholism, the more acute the emerging problems become. The relationship between the level of alcohol consumption and morbidity rates, as well as mortality and crime resulting from intoxication and alcoholism, plays a significant role.

The causes of alcohol consumption and chronic alcoholism include: a person's attempts to temporarily forget about existing problems through alcohol consumption, and as a result, their weakness increases, leading to alcohol addiction; a person's frustration from alcohol due to serious problems in life or career and "breaking"; the abundance of idle time in the family among children and young people and lack of parental control over it; young people try to stand out from others, trying to demonstrate their behavior unlike others through open drinking; children and young people become addicted to alcohol after seeing guests off at home, trying or secretly drinking the remaining alcoholic beverages, including vodka, wine, or beer; a person's desire to consume alcohol again arises as a result of the body's pleasure and delight from consuming it; parents give their child more money than they need and do not control its expenditure, etc.

When organizing preventive work with persons suffering from chronic alcoholism, attention should be paid to: collecting information about persons suffering from chronic alcoholism in the territory of the mahalla with the help of street leaders, heads of households, and other persons; identifying and studying, if necessary, with the participation of a psychologist-specialist, the needs, interests, problems related to the person and their life; conducting an individual educational and preventive conversation with the person, taking into account their needs, interests, and problems; assigning a public mentor to a person suffering from chronic alcoholism and assisting in their reintegration into society; providing, if necessary, social, legal, medical, psychological, and other practical assistance, as well as applying to authorized bodies to resolve identified problems.

During the educational and preventive measures carried out in this regard, explaining to the individual, especially minors and young people, the harm of alcohol consumption to the human body, its terrible consequences, with the help of a specialist doctor, religious scholars, and mahalla activists, can serve positively to prevent alcohol consumption in the individual.

It should not be forgotten that when studying the reasons for a person's alcoholism, it is important to study whether there are people in their lineage who are addicted to alcohol.

In conclusion, it should be noted that today, in the fight against crime and the early prevention of offenses, it is advisable, first of all, to systematically study and analyze the criminogenic situation in administrative territories, as well as to timely identify, analyze, and eliminate the causes of crimes and the conditions contributing to their commission, especially in the context of the transition to a market economy and civil society, to take consistent preventive measures aimed at eliminating the main criminogenic determinants of crimes - unemployment, immorality, dependency, chronic alcoholism

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